

EXTREME TEACHING-LEARNING A RESPONSIVE METHODOLOGY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Quality has become a grave concern in higher education today. Many colleges and universities still follow the traditional teacher-centered pedagogy, which has failed to enhance quality of student learning. The paper proposes an extreme Teaching-Learning Paradigm (XTLP) framework to improve quality in higher education. XTLP derives its philosophy from Extreme Programming, an agile software methodology intended to improve software quality in response to the changing requirements of customers. XTLP aims at continuous improvement of student learning, keeping student satisfaction as its focus. Through its many practices, it intends to overcome many of the limitations of the traditional teaching-learning paradigm. This paper describes the XTLP, a conceptual framework with its practices and discusses its usability in higher education.

Keywords: *Extreme Programming; higher education; pedagogy; teaching and learning; XTLP.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian higher education system is one of the largest in the world. In spite of its vast network, quality in higher education still remains elusive. According to Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings of 2013, none of the Indian Universities feature in the top 200 [1]. As per the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) report of 2010, 62% of the Universities and 90% of the colleges are average or below average. According to industry reports only about 15% of college graduates acquire the required skills to become employable. The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education is far below the global average [2].

Academic institutions, at the input end, have student and at the output end, industry. However there is frustration at both ends. There is very little collaboration between academia and industry. The university curriculum does not prepare students in employability skills. There is too little effort taken by the teaching faculty, to assess student needs, aptitude, personality types, to make teaching relevant, interesting and flexible.

Of the many factors that lead to decreased quality in higher education, a dominant factor is the traditional teacher-centered transmittal model of teaching and learning [3]. Teacher is portrayed 'as a sage on the stage', who has the knowledge and transmits this knowledge to students. Students turn out to be passive learners [4]. Much of the teaching is lecture-based chalk and talk. Students are assessed on their capacity to memorize and reproduce in the exams as per what they are taught during the course [5]. There is limited scope for students to interact, discuss issues and ideas, analyse and apply concepts to real life situations. Student learning is individualistic and competitive.

Adherence to curriculum and completion of syllabus before the exams appears to be the overriding concern of the faculty.

Extreme Programming which is a type of agile software development methodology has been successful in software industry producing high quality software in response to the changing requirements of the customer. It uses many simple practices based on the core values: simplicity, communication, feedback and courage to deliver the software product iteratively and incrementally [6]. The core practices of XP can very well be adapted to higher education in order to overcome many of the deficiencies of traditional teaching-learning methods. This paper proposes eXtreme Teaching-Learning Paradigm (XTLP), a conceptual framework based on XP philosophy to improve quality in higher education.

II. EXTREME PROGRAMMING PRACTICES

- 1) Onsite Customer: During the entire cycle of software development, the customer is always available to the developers to provide immediate feedback and clarify requirements.
- 2) Short Releases: A simple workable system is put into production quickly and later new versions of the system are released in short cycles to the customer incrementally.
- 3) Planning Game: The planning game is played between the developers and customers at the beginning of the project and after every successive release to integrate business priorities and technical estimates for the upcoming release.
- 4) Simple Design: The purpose of simple design is to make the product easily adaptable for future changes. Developers solve customers' expressed present requirements without guessing what the future requirements may arise.
- 5) Pair Programming: In pair programming two programmers join together to solve the problem collaboratively. In this way the knowledge, ideas are exchanged between the partners.
- 6) Collective Ownership: The purpose is to make the entire team responsible for the code. The code belongs to everyone; hence any member of the team is free to make necessary changes in the code in order to add value to it.
- 7) Continuous Integration: The code written by different pairs is integrated frequently which helps in fixing the bugs quickly and early.
- 8) Coding Standards: These are coding guidelines that refer to uniformity in programming style which helps the programmers to understand each other better.
- 9) Test Driven Development: In Test Driven Development (TDD), the developer writes the test case first and then implements the code to pass the test. The developer first thinks 'what' to implement before trying 'how' to implement.
- 10) Refactoring: The purpose of this practice is to keep the design and the code simple. It refers to restructuring the code by simplifying the complex logic without changing the external behavior of the code.
- 11) 40-Hour Week: The purpose of this practice is to maintain sustainable pace with the project without working overtime.
- 12) Metaphor: The purpose of Metaphor is to guide everyone associated with the project with a simple shared story of how the system functions.

III. EXTREME TEACHING-LEARNING PRACTICES

From the twelve practices of Extreme Programming, the authors extract five practices and translate them into educational practices of XTLP framework. They are: Goal Driven Teaching, Pair Learning, Continuous Assessment, Planning Meeting and 40-Hour Week. The following section describes these practices.

A. Goal Driven Teaching

This practice is a translation of TDD of XP. In TDD, each programming unit starts with a test case written. For this the developer must clearly know what the output should be. Then the test case is run to fail. In the next step, the code is written such that it passes the test case. If the test fails, code is revised to make run the test case. After the

test case runs successfully, code refactoring may be done and new test cases are written. The basic steps of TDD cycle are creating a test case, writing code and running the test.

Goal Driven Teaching (GDT) too follows similar steps. In GDT, learning goals and objectives are specified at the beginning of the instruction for every lecture unit. The instructional content is designed and delivered based on these learning goals and objectives. To test whether students have achieved the specified learning objectives, a quick and short evaluation in the form of formative assessment is conducted after the instruction on a particular topic or a group of related topics is delivered. From the formative evaluation, the instructor can identify the areas where a student has failed to meet the learning objectives and the areas where he has achieved success and accordingly revise the instruction [7]. This will help the instructor to develop new assignments, coursework, lecture notes, power point presentations and also revise instruction delivery method so that the students are expected to perform much better in the next class or course. Brown et al. [8] highlight that formative assessment is most effective when it is 'timely, relevant and meaningful'.

B. Pair Learning

In pair learning two students sit together side by side to work on an academic task designed by the teacher. One takes the role of a 'driver', who actually solves the problem with a pen and book or a keyboard and monitor. The other takes the role of a 'navigator' who works as a reviewer, closely watching the work done by the driver, presents ideas, suggestions for improvement and also points out errors or mistakes. When the driver works on the details of the task, the navigator keeps holistic picture of the task in mind. The driver and navigator switch their roles regularly.

Pair learning is a special case of cooperative learning where the size of the group is fixed for two. Johnson et al. [9] who did prolonged research on the effectiveness of cooperative learning identified five essential elements of cooperative learning: positive interdependence, promotive face-to-face interaction, individual accountability, social skills, and group processing. Since pair learning is a special kind of co-operative learning, the above elements will also be applicable to pair learning.

C. Continuous Assessment

Just as in XP, a product is incrementally delivered in short cycles, the learning in a student is assessed continuously in short cycles in the form of summative assessments. Rather than having one long assessment at the end of the course, many assessments are conducted frequently during the course. Summative assessment differs from the formative assessment in that, summative assessment contributes to the grade of a student [10]. The summative assessments can take various forms such as assignments, quizzes, tests, projects, exams, seminars etc. CA also contains a component of formative assessment, i.e., apart from grading a student it also provides valuable feedback to both the student as well as the faculty. CA promotes incremental learning in a student.

D. Planning Meeting

The purpose of planning meeting in XTLP is to bring together the developers and customers of education around the table to plan, design and evaluate a course. Planning meeting is conducted at two different levels. At the first level, it is a meeting of the faculty, subject matter experts, people from industry, alumni etc. who are all stakeholders in education to design a new course or revise an existing course. The meeting is aimed at bringing formal changes in the curriculum design. The meeting takes place prior to the commencement of the course. At the second level, it is a meeting of faculty and students that takes place during the course. Faculty members take the role of developers and students take the role of customers. In the meeting, students will assess whether goals and objectives of the course have been achieved, offer suggestions for improvement. Faculty in turn estimate the feasibility of implementing student suggestions within the framework of available resources, scope, quality and time schedule. This planning meeting is a periodic activity. Not necessarily that it should be done to make new plans. The existing plans could be reviewed or reworked in order to meet the course objectives. The planning meeting held during the course, helps to

bring about informal changes in the syllabus. Inmaculada Plaza et al. [11] in their research investigated that informal changes in curriculum can bring about continuous improvement in university education.

E. 40-hour week

Time is a valuable resource. Students should learn to manage their time effectively. They are required to put in 40 hours of academic work in a week. This includes the time spent in attending the classes as well as the time spent outside the class hours in study, doing coursework and any other academic work. There is a general tendency, especially among the students in higher education to spend more time in socialization and less time in actual study when there are no assignments to be submitted or exams to be answered. On the contrary, before or during the exams they spend long hours in study without giving sufficient rest to body or mind. In both cases, quality of study is affected. Mind needs to be fresh and alert for reflection, creativity and critical thinking. Sticking to a schedule of 40 hours a week, helps one to sustain the quality of learning.

IV. ADVANTAGES OF XTLP

XTLP tries to overcome many of the problems in the higher education system. The following section describes how this new framework would address these problems.

Higher success rate: One of the limitations of the traditional teaching-learning methodology is its long teaching-learning cycle. Students are often assessed at the end of the semester by one long durational final exam. Students are declared passed or failed based on the performance in that exam. This is typical like quality control in a factory setting where defective products are separated after the production. Just like manufacturing companies, would like to produce zero defect products, educational institutions too need to strive to produce zero failures. Companies have been using quality assurance mechanism to continuously improve the quality of the products through short cycles of delivery. XTLP focuses on quality assurance of educational process by short cycles of teaching learning through continuous assessments.

Up-to-date curriculum: It is observed that in higher education, syllabi remain the same for many years. XTLP engages stakeholders of education, throughout the teaching learning process. In the 'Planning Meeting', students assess the curriculum, teaching, assessment and give valuable feedback. Students are the customers of education and they want fresh product. Students' needs, suggestions are taken seriously by the faculty to incorporate necessary changes in the instruction. The planning meeting is also conducted with subject experts and industry experts to design relevant and useful courses.

Developing employability skills: Today employers look for multiple skills in the students to hire them for industry. Apart from knowledge and technical skills, they look for social skills such as leadership, communication, team work and personal skills such as self confidence, commitment, motivation etc. XTLP aims at developing these skills in the students during their study. It advocates 'pair learning' as a cooperative learning strategy, where students learn in pairs. In pair learning, students have to interact with each other for completing academic tasks. This helps the students to develop both social as well as personal skills apart from acquiring knowledge of the subjects.

Increased motivation: It is common to find many students having poor attendance in colleges. Students are not motivated to attend the classes because they find teaching boring as most of the teaching is didactic. XTLP makes learning interesting and fun through 'pair learning'. The practice of 'goal driven teaching' helps the faculty to assess student progression, motivation etc. so that they can make relevant changes in their teaching to make it interesting and useful. These practices would generate interest and motivation in the students so that they would not miss lectures and run short of attendance.

Reduced scope slips: In traditional teaching-learning paradigm, one of the risks is the scope slips. The scope in an educational scenario refers to the syllabus designed for each course. As both time (duration of the course) and scope are fixed, to maintain high quality of learning, the scope needs to be balanced with time from the beginning of the course. However in practice, due to its long teaching-learning cycle, there is a risk of scope slip at the beginning of

the course schedule, as a result students are forced to put in additional time and effort just before the close of the semester to complete the syllabus. This is likely to affect the quality of learning in students. XTLP intends to address this risk, through its short teaching-learning cycles. The scope and time are kept in balance from the beginning of a course so that the risk of scope slips is substantially minimized.

V. TRADITIONAL PARADIGM Vs EXTREME PARADIGM

There are significant differences between the traditional teaching-learning paradigm and XTLP which are highlighted in the table below.

1	One long teaching-learning cycle.	Many short teaching-learning cycles.
2	Teaching and learning is rigid.	Teaching and learning is flexible and adaptable.
3	Teaching-learning is linear and incremental.	Teaching-learning is iterative and incremental.
4	Students are mostly assessed by one final exam. Students are burdened with vast syllabus to study. If they fail, there is no way to make up.	Students are assessed continuously. Due to regular assessments, students have limited syllabus to study for each assessment. There is scope for make up in the next assessment.
5	Learner stress and anxiety is high towards the end of the course.	Learner stress and anxiety is minimal throughout the course.
6	Teachers are the transmitters of knowledge.	Teachers act as facilitators. Students construct knowledge by synthesizing information and collaborating with peers.
7	Students learn individually and learning is competitive.	Students learn in pairs and learning is co-operative.
8	There is less emphasis on formative assessment. Faculty find difficult to know whether students are in pace with teaching.	Student learning is monitored through continuous formative assessments. It guides the faculty to align teaching material or method according to student progression.
9	Testing is done on the instructional content after it is delivered.	Instructional content is designed or revised after testing.
10	Teachers decide what students should learn and how they should learn. Students learn what teachers teach.	Students are involved in the process of design, implementation and assessment of instruction. Teachers teach what students need.
11	Only students are considered as learners.	Both teachers and students are considered as learners.
12	Learning and assessment are separate.	Assessment is a part of learning process.

VI. CONCLUSION

XTLP is a student-centered methodology for teaching learning in higher education. Student satisfaction is the governing principle. Student is the focal point. Student satisfaction has a ripple effect. When students are satisfied, the faculty, administration, parents and employers too will be satisfied.

What is extreme about XTLP? Just as Kent Beck says that he did not invent new practices in XP, but took the existing practices in software development to the extreme level [6], it can be said that the XTLP practices are not newly invented practices. These are already used in various teaching-learning models. They are only taken to the extreme level, such as continuous assessment, continuous feedback, continuous student involvement, continuous revision of instruction etc.

XTLP is a general framework for teaching and learning in higher education. Its concepts and practices can be easily implemented in classroom teaching in higher education. Its core practices are drawn from XP and mapped to the best practices in the existing teaching-learning methodologies. XTLP framework aims at bringing innovation in the classroom teaching. Its sole purpose is to enhance the quality of learning in the classroom teaching and address many of the shortcomings of the traditional teaching-learning paradigm.

REFERENCES

- [1] “Top 200 QS World University Rankings 2013,” Available: <http://www.theguardian.com/highereducationnetwork/table/2013/sep/10/qs-world-university-rankings-2013> [Aug. 10, 2014].
- [2] “Higher Education in India: Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012–2017) and beyond,” Available: [http://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAssets/Higher_Education_in_India/\\$File/EY-FICC_Higher_Education_Report_Nov12.pdf](http://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAssets/Higher_Education_in_India/$File/EY-FICC_Higher_Education_Report_Nov12.pdf) [Jul. 19, 2014].
- [3] M. Weimer, *Learner-Centered Teaching: Fiv Key Changes to Practice*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass, 2002.
- [4] A. King, “From sage on the stage to guide on the side,” *College Teaching*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp 30-35, 1993.
- [5] D.P. Kauchak and P.D. Eggen, *Learning and Teaching: Research-based Methods*, 3rd ed. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon, 1998.
- [6] K. Beck, *Extreme Programming Explained: Embrace Change*. Addison- Wesley, 1999.
- [7] P. Black and D. William, *Assessment and classroom learning*, “Assessment in Education, Principles, Policy and Practice”, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 7–73, 1998.
- [8] G. Brown, J. Bull and M. Pendelbury, *Assessing Student Learning in Higher Education*. London: Routledge, 1997.
- [9] D.W. Johnson, R.T. Johnson and K.A. Smith, *Active Learning: Cooperation in the College Classroom*. Edina, MN: Interaction, 1991.
- [10] M. Yorke, “Formative assessment in higher education: moves towards theory and the enhancement of pedagogic practice,” *Higher Education*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 477-501, 2003.
- [11] I. Plaza, R.Igual, C. Medrano and M.Á.Rubio, “From companies to universities: application of R&D&I concepts in higher education teaching,” *IEEE Trans. Edu.*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 308-315, 2013.